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A Baseline Study of Macroinvertebrate Communities of McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek (Olentangy River Watershed) Prior to Over-Wide Ditch Construction

Final Report

**Upper Olentangy River Watershed Project
Project Number 05(h)-L763A**

by

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Executive Summary

This study was a component of a larger effort to characterize habitats and biota in a first-order stream prior to construction of an “over-wide” ditch in a segment of the stream within the Upper Olentangy River watershed in central Ohio. Funding for the project was provided through a Section 319 grant from the USEPA and Ohio EPA with a state contribution from Ohio DNR, Division of Soil and Water Conservation. Over-wide ditch construction was planned in McKibben Ditch (HUC 05060001-110-02), which in the study area drains from 2.3 to 4.4 square miles of mostly agricultural land in eastern Marion County and western Morrow County.

Four 61-meter (200-foot) stream reaches were selected for study in McKibben Ditch: one immediately above the planned over-wide ditch, one within the upstream end and another within the downstream end of the construction area, and the fourth immediately below the planned over-wide ditch. A reach of the same length in Riffle Creek, also tributary to the Olentangy River in Marion County, with a drainage area of 4.8 square miles, was selected as a reference site that has undergone traditional ditch maintenance in the past. Habitat assessment and macroinvertebrate sampling were conducted at each site in July 2006 and July 2007. Habitat characteristics and quality were recorded using Ohio EPA’s Headwater Habitat Evaluation Form. Each site was divided into two contiguous reaches of 30.5 meters (100 feet) each for macroinvertebrate sampling. Macroinvertebrates were collected from each 30.5-m reach with qualitative sampling methods and a semi-quantitative method derived from rapid biomonitoring methods of the USEPA.

Sampling in July 2006 was hampered by flooding, whereas during a drought in July 2007 the two upstream sites in McKibben Ditch contained no surface water. Stream habitat quality throughout the study area was degraded, as indicated by the nearly total lack of tree canopy, lack of within-channel habitat diversity, and channel substrate consisting almost entirely of very soft, fine-grained sediment. Channel substrate diversity was slightly greater at the two most downstream sites in McKibben ditch, and the most downstream site had a small amount of canopy cover.

Midge larvae comprised the most diverse group of macroinvertebrates, contributing 38 of the 126 macroinvertebrate taxa, and they contributed over 10% of the individuals in most of the semi-quantitative samples each year. The sites with the most taxa differed between 2006 and 2007, but Riffle Creek had the lowest number of taxa both years. Replicate samples (from contiguous 30.5-m reaches at each site) usually, but not always, revealed similar numbers of taxa. An extensive reach of McKibben Ditch in the lower part of the study area revealed increased in-channel habitat diversity because of the presence of a broken clay tile main in the channel. Fingernail clams, oligochaete worms, snails, and midge larvae were the most abundant groups, though in various proportions, at all sites both years, and “clean water indicator” taxa (mayflies, caddisflies and stoneflies) were rare or absent.

Continuous monitoring of the surface hydrology of the sites on McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek should be undertaken to provide detailed information on the extent to which the sites contain continuous or intermittent flow, and if intermittent, the seasonal timing of surface flow. Such information will be critical in detecting changes in hydrology and interpreting results of habitat and biological assessments that might be scheduled following completion of over-wide ditch construction. The habitat evaluations conducted in 2006 and 2007 will be useful for detecting changes in habitat structure and quality following construction, and no additional evaluations during the construction period are needed. Fish community surveys and QHEI results should be integrated with the results reported here in order to provide a broader understanding of the state of aquatic communities in McKibben Ditch prior to construction.

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Introduction

Ohio lies at the eastern end of America's Corn Belt. As such, much of the land area of the state has been converted for agriculture, and the productivity of that agricultural land relies heavily on drainage of water from the landscape. As noted in the Quality Assurance Project Plan (QAPP) for this project submitted by The Ohio State University, "There are more than 60,000 miles of streams in Ohio with approximately 22,500 miles considered drainage ditches. Approximately 4,000 miles of Ohio's drainage ditches are under some form of maintenance (Sanders, 2000)." The QAPP (pp. 3-4) also states:

Concerns about sustaining the viability of agricultural production systems, maintenance costs, water quality issues and habitat degradation are causing growing conflict between various sectors of society and, in particular, the agricultural community and environmental organizations. Clearly, there is a need to identify the system capacities that best serve all interests and the benefits/impacts of exceeding those capacities over space or time. Specifically, we are interested in the capacity of modified headwater channel systems (i.e., drainage ditches) to sustain ecological integrity and function in landscapes with intensive agriculture or urbanization . . . This project addresses a very sensitive issue for agricultural producers, county drainage managers, engineers, and natural resources managers in the Olentangy River watershed: balancing the historic tradition of extensive drainage ditch networks to sustain the region's agricultural productivity with the development of new drainage management technologies that will help restore the watershed to some degree of improved ecological quality.

The general project area is the Upper Olentangy River (HUC 05060001-110) in central Ohio. Implementation of modified ("over-wide") ditch construction was to be undertaken in McKibben Ditch (HUC 05060001-110-020), a first-order (*sensu* Strahler) tributary that flows directly into the Olentangy River in Marion County (Figure 1). This project is many-faceted, and stream habitat assessment and aquatic invertebrate community characterization comprised two components. The goals and objectives of the over-all project are quoted below from the QAPP (pp. 4-5).

The overall goal of this project is to assist the ODNR-DSWC with the monitoring and reporting of stream protection and restoration efforts in the Upper Olentangy River watershed, a sub-basin of the Upper Scioto River watershed (HUC 05060001). These efforts will be conducted in concert with the Scioto River Conservation Reserve Enhancement Program (CREP) and local watershed planning and conservation programs. Activities of this project will fulfill the *Monitoring and Assessment* component of a larger effort funded by a Section 319 grant from the USEPA and the Ohio EPA, and a state contribution by the ODNR-DSWC. Specific goals of the project identified by the ODNR-DSWC include:

- 1) Contribute to 80% aquatic life use attainments within the Upper Olentangy watershed.

- 2) Demonstrate the value of collaboration and program integration for watershed protection with special emphasis on the impacts of the Scioto CREP.
- 3) Monitor, evaluate and report on the effectiveness of select best management practices at specific project sites.

Primary objectives for the project are to:

- 1) Assess benefits/impacts to biology, chemistry, hydrology, and geomorphology of installing an over-wide ditch design in McKibben Ditch, located in the Upper Olentangy watershed, in lieu of a traditional ditch maintenance practice or no maintenance;
- 2) Assess benefits/impacts to biology, chemistry, hydrology, and geomorphology when an alternative maintenance practice is coupled with other best management practices such as grassed waterways, buffer strips, and controlled drainage management; and
- 3) Compare an over-wide ditch design in a predominantly agricultural landscape to the same design in a predominantly urban landscape, to a natural channel design, to a traditional clean-out or maintenance, and to an “undisturbed” reference reach.

The implementation project also will build on knowledge, primarily based on work conducted by members of this collaborative partnership, that suggests: (1) development of fluvial features in modified channels is predictable; (2) the ability to sustain ecosystems in modified and constructed channel systems is more a function of the fluvial features and vegetation within the channels than land use management practices along the top of the banks; and (3) existing traditional maintenance or clean-out practices that disrupt successional development of channel ecosystems have a yet-to-be-quantified impact on water quality and ecology. We anticipate that the proposed project will provide needed integration of geomorphology, hydrology, biology, and water chemistry to watershed-scale guidance for management of the Upper Scioto sub-watersheds, in particular, the Upper Olentangy River watersheds.

The specific objectives of the aquatic invertebrate community component of the project, assuming timely implementation of the ditch construction phase, were (1) to assess the diversity and abundance of the community prior to installation of the ditch maintenance practices in McKibben Ditch, including the stream reaches above, within, and downstream of the practices; (2) to assess changes in the diversity and abundance of the community in response to the practices; and (3) to compare the invertebrate community in McKibben Ditch to that in nearby Riffle Creek, which was to serve as a reference stream in the sense that it has undergone traditional ditch maintenance. Objectives (1) and (3) were accomplished; however, ditch construction was not begun by May 2008. When a delay in construction became apparent late in 2006, we extended pre-construction assessment of the invertebrate communities to a second summer, which permitted us to document year-to-year variations in habitat and community characteristics and thereby greatly improve our ability to discern changes following construction. Therefore, the invertebrate communities were sampled in the summers of both 2006 and 2007 and no post-construction comparisons could be made. Herein, we report our findings on the baseline habitat conditions and aquatic invertebrate community composition in McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek.

Study Area

The two streams examined in this study lie within the Eastern Corn Belt Plains ecoregion (OEPA 1987, p. 2-3) and are tributaries of the Olentangy River in central Ohio. Both streams flow generally southward and are directly influenced by adjacent agricultural practices as well as suburban land-use upstream of the sampling locations. Five sites were selected (Figure 1) for collection of macroinvertebrates and habitat assessment to coincide with those used for the fish surveys and chemical analyses performed in complementary studies by Ohio State University scientists. Four of the sites were in McKibben Ditch: one site upstream of the proposed over-wide ditch installation (“upstream”), one site in the upstream portion of the proposed over-wide ditch installation (“over-wide upstream”), one site in the lower portion of the proposed over-wide ditch installation (“over-wide downstream”), and one site downstream of the proposed over-wide ditch installation (“downstream”). The fifth site, used as a reference site, was located in Riffle Creek immediately upstream of State Route 98. The watershed areas upstream from each sampling site ranged from 2.3 square miles to 4.4 square miles (Table 1).

Figure 1. Locations of study sites in the Olentangy River watershed

Each site consisted of a 61 m (200 ft) reach of channel and was at least 30.5 m (100 ft) upstream and downstream from any road or bridge crossing. Each site was subdivided into two adjacent reaches of 30.5 m (100 ft) – identified as “reach A” (downstream reach) and “reach B” (upstream reach).

Figure 2. McKibben Ditch study sites showing locations of sampling reaches A and B

Figure 3. Vegetation in the McKibben Ditch downstream (upper left), over-wide downstream (upper right), over-wide upstream (lower left), and Riffle Creek (lower right) study sites, July 2006

All study sites exhibited vegetated banks (figure 3 and 4); however, the density and taxonomic richness of vegetation at the sites, as well as the amount of channel vegetation and canopy cover, did vary among the sites. Grasses and occasional shrubs typified the bank vegetation, except at the banks of the “downstream” site, which were heavily colonized by large trees. Details of the habitat and vegetation at each site are described in the Results section.

The habitat surveys and macroinvertebrate sampling were conducted during baseflow conditions. All sites were similar in channel flow characteristics with one exception: the over-wide downstream site had sections of broken clay drainage tile embedded in the channel that caused flows within that portion of the ditch to become intermittently subterranean. Consequently, the over-wide downstream site exhibited a more heterogeneous habitat containing more pools than sites with open flow, especially in 2007. During July 2006, a period of higher-than-normal rainfall produced flooding in both Riffle Creek and McKibben Ditch. This caused postponement of sampling at the two upstream-most sites in McKibben ditch and in Riffle Creek until later in July to allow the water to recede to baseflow conditions. During July 2007 and continuing until October of that year, a period of drought resulted in no surface water at the upstream and over-wide upstream sites of McKibben Ditch, so no macroinvertebrate sampling was performed at those sites that year.

Methods

Macroinvertebrate samples were collected on 6, 7, 10, and 19 July 2006 and again on 5, 9, and 10 July 2007. Initial locations of sampling sites in July 2006 were identified using vinyl flags inserted along the stream banks to mark each 30.5m (100 ft) reach (reaches A and B). The flags were then geo-located using a Garmin Etrex handheld WAAS-enabled GPS unit and longitude and latitude readings were recorded (Appendix B). Digital photos of the sites were also taken at that time. In July 2007, the GPS locations were used to find all of the flags from the previous year to ensure consistent sampling between years. The lead scientist and a research associate were assisted by one of several undergraduate research assistants to perform sampling at all sites both years to ensure consistency of effort.

Physicochemical data were collected immediately prior to biological sampling. Readings were taken at the downstream end of reaches A and B at each site. Air and water temperatures and concentration and percent saturation of dissolved oxygen (DO) were measured using a YSI Model 58 DO meter. The YSI 5739 DO probe was calibrated in air according to the manufacturer’s recommended procedures. Conductivity was measured using an Oakton CON 100 Series field conductivity meter calibrated daily in the laboratory with a standard conductivity solution of 447 $\mu\text{mhos}/\text{cm}$ at 25°C and pH was measured using a Cole-Parmer Digi-Sense Model 5938-00 field pH meter calibrated daily in the laboratory using pH 7.00 and pH 10.00 buffers.

Two methods of macroinvertebrate sampling were employed. Qualitative and semi-quantitative samples were composited separately for each reach beginning at the downstream end of reach A and progressing upstream. Qualitative sampling was performed by two members of the team using small rectangular (8 cm x 11 cm) 0.50 mm mesh nets, forceps, and by “hand-picking” to collect specimens from all representative habitat types within each site (Figure 4).

Sampling was continued for 30-60 minutes until no new taxa were discovered within a reach. Qualitative specimens collected by both technicians were combined for a given reach into wide-mouth 500 mL polyethylene jars containing 100% ethanol as they were collected.

Figure 4. Qualitative sampling in the McKibben Ditch upstream site, July 2006

Semi-quantitative sampling was accomplished using a modification of the US EPA Rapid Bioassessment Protocol (RBP) Method 7.2 for Benthic Macroinvertebrates: Multi-habitat Approach, Fixed Distance Designation (Barbour et al. 1999). Working immediately upstream of the qualitative sampling team, the lead scientist used a 0.50 mm mesh, 30.5 cm-wide D-frame dip net to sample the top several cm of sediment in the stream channel. Approximately 10 “jabs” of sediment approximately 0.6 m in length were collected for each 30.5 m reach and composited in an HDPE 20-L bucket. The bucket contents were then rinsed through the D-frame net to reduce the amount of water to be transported. The remaining sample contents were placed into 4-L plastic zip-lock bags and preserved with approximately equal volumes of 100% ethanol.

Land-use and habitat characteristics for each site were evaluated and recorded using Ohio EPA’s Primary Headwater Habitat Evaluation (HHEI) Form (OEPA 2002) (Appendix A) immediately after biological sampling. This assessment involved estimation of the percent of channel substrate components (e.g., boulders, cobble, gravel), measurements of pool depths, bank-full width, riparian width, land-use on the floodplain, sinuosity, noting the presence of aquatic vertebrates, and several other metrics. Vegetation differences were noted and canopy cover was estimated. The team previewed the HHEI criteria prior to commencement of biological sampling to be sure none of the attributes would be obscured during sampling.

Specimen identification for all samples was performed upon return to the laboratory following each July sampling event. Both qualitative and semi-quantitative samples were first preprocessed and sorted.

Qualitative specimens were preprocessed by removing them from the sample jars, examining them under 6-10x power using dissecting microscopes, and sorting them by taxonomic groups into glass vials containing a storage solution of AGW (85% ethanol, 5% glycerin solution, 10% reverse-osmosis-treated (RO) water; by volume).

Semi-quantitative sample preprocessing involved a series of steps to remove debris and subsequent sieving. Samples were removed by hand from the zip-lock bags and placed on wire hardware cloth (5.5 mm openings) resting in white plastic dish pans. Samples were rinsed with a gentle flow of tap water, large debris was removed by hand, and specimens retained in the wire mesh were stored in >60% ethanol in 500 mL wide-mouth jars. Materials passing through the hardware cloth were then sieved through a No. 40 (mesh 0.425 mm) brass sieve, and retained specimens were separated from debris before being stored in >60% ethanol in 500 mL wide-mouth jars. All materials passing through the No. 40 sieve were discarded. Subsampling was performed on specimens retained on the hardware cloth using a Folsom Plankton Splitter when it was determined that more than 200 specimens were present for any 30.5 m reach composite sample. Subsamples were stored in 500 mL wide-mouth jars in >60% ethanol. Specimens in the wide-mouth jars were next examined using dissecting microscopes, sorted taxonomically, and stored in glass vials in AGW.

When more than 50 specimens of any one taxon were present in a composite sample vial, subsampling was performed using a 250 mL glass culture dish or petri dish divided into eighths; portions were selected for further identification using a random number table to select eighths, including enough eighths to provide approximately 50 individuals. Midge larvae (Chironomidae) were digested in a 10% KOH solution, rinsed, mounted on microscope slides in a CMCP medium, and covered with glass cover slips.

After preprocessing, all specimens were keyed to genus or higher level using taxonomic keys (see Literature Cited) and a voucher collection was prepared. The lead scientist confirmed the identifications of all voucher specimens.

Results

Habitat Characteristics

The condition in July 2006 and 2007 of most of the habitat features included on the Headwaters Habitat Evaluation Index form is shown in Table 1. Out of a maximum possible score of 100, the scores at most sites (all 61 m long) both years ranged between 58 and 67. The two exceptions were the upstream and over-wide upstream sites in 2007, when neither contained any surface water, with scores of 35 and 37, respectively. At that time the pool depth scores were 0 rather than 20 or 25 as recorded at all other sites both years. The channel substrate types at the upstream, over-wide upstream, and Riffle Creek sites were limited almost entirely to very soft, fine-grained silt, muck, and/or detritus that collectively covered 98% to 100% of the channel area. By contrast, the over-wide downstream and downstream sites possessed 7 or 8 substrate types, but even there the percentages of boulders, cobble, and bedrock (considered high-quality substrates) contributed less than 10% (estimated at 24% in 2007 at the over-wide downstream site, perhaps because of very low water levels).

Habitat and biological assessments were interrupted in July 2006 by flooding. Therefore, macroinvertebrate samples were collected at three McKibben ditch sites on 6, 7, or 10 July but were not collected at the upstream and Riffle Creek sites until 19 July. The summer of 2007, by

Table 1. Habitat characteristics and scores of Headwaters Habitat Evaluation Index metrics. Refer to Appendix A. All sites are in McKibben Ditch except where designated Riffle Creek.

Site Habitat Characteristic or Score / Year	Up		Over-Wide Up		Over-Wide Down		Down		Riffle Creek	
	2006	2007	2006	2007	2006	2007	2006	2007	2006	2007
Drainage Area, square miles	2.3		2.3		4.4		4.4		4.3	
River Mile	2.75		2.65		1.4		1.2		4.8	
Date	10 July*	9 July	10 July	9 July	6 July	5 July	7 July	5 July	19 July	10 July
Substrate Type Score	6	3	6	3	9	6	6	6	6	3
No. of Substrate Types Score	2	2	2	4	8	7	7	7	2	3
Pool Depth Score	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	25
Bank Full Width Score	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
HHEI Score (Sum of Above)	58	35	58	37	67	63	63	63	58	61
Stream Channel Modifications	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering	recov- ering
Maximum Pool Depth, cm	50	0	67	0	37	>30	53	41	50	17, no pools
Two Predominant Substrates	silt 98%, hardpan 2%	silt 99%, woody debris <1%	silt 66%, fine detri- tus 34%	silt 99%, woody debris <1%	silt 45%, sand 45%	silt 60%, artificial 15%	silt 90%, sand 5%	silt 83%, fine detri- tus 8%	silt 99%, fine detri- tus <1%	muck 50%, silt 49%
Total Percent of Boulders, Cobble, Bedrock	0	0	0	0	3	24	9	8	0	0
In-Channel Vegetation	None	Grass, shrubs	Grass growing in channel; "monoto- nous"	Grass growing in channel	Grass growing in most of channel; 2-3 small shrubs	None, overhang- ing grass	None	None, overhang- ing grass	A few <i>Sagittaria</i> , <i>Spargan- ium</i> , sedge	Floating algal mats over 1/3 of surface; several <i>Sagittaria</i> , <i>Typha</i>

Table 1. Continued.

Site Habitat Characteristic or Score / Year	Up		Over-Wide Up		Over-Wide Down		Down		Riffle Creek	
	2006	2007	2006	2007	2006	2007	2006	2007	2006	2007
Ave. Bank-Full Width, meters	6.0	6.8	5.0	5.4	7.6	9.9	8.6	11.1	11.3	11.3
Riparian Width, R, L Bank, m	none, none	none, none	none, none	none, none	none, none	<5-none, <5-none	<5, <5	<5, <5	none, none	none, none
Floodplain Quality, R, L sides	Both - shrub & old field	Both - shrub & old field	Both - open pasture/ row crop	Both - open pasture/ row crop	Both - open pasture/ row crop	Both - open pasture/ row crop	Both - open pasture/ row crop	Both - open pasture/ row crop	Both - open pasture/ row crop	Both - open pasture/ row crop
Flow Regime at time of evaluation	Stream flowing (slight)	Dry channel – no water	Stream flowing (not apparent)	Dry channel – no water	Subsurf. w/isolated pools	Subsurf. w/isolated pools	Stream flowing	Stream flowing	Stream flowing	Stream flowing
Sinuosity (bends/61 m of channel)	2.0	0.5	None	None	None	Nones	None	None	None	None
Estimated Stream Gradient	Flat to Moderate	Flat	Flat to Moderate	Flat	Flat to Moderate	Flat	Flat	Flat	Flat to Moderate	Flat
Percent of Canopy Open	100	100	100	100	100	97	95	85	100	100
Canopy Composition	None	None	None	None	None	Couple of small willows	small trees, shrubs	small trees, shrubs	None	None
Fish Observed?	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Frogs or Tadpoles Observed?	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Salamanders Observed?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

*Biological samples were collected on 19 July 2006.

contrast, was marked by a prolonged drought. The upstream and over-wide upstream sites possessed no standing or flowing water in July 2007 and were “dry” until at least October (J. D’Ambrosio, OSU, personal communication, January 2008), while the over-wide downstream site possessed a series of isolated pools, some of which had no obvious flow and others of which had visible flow as water exited a broken tile main and re-entered the main a few feet away. The downstream and Riffle Creek sites maintained continuous but very low flow at least through the time of our biological sampling.

All sites possessed a flat to moderate gradient (Table 1) and virtually no canopy cover (overhanging trees), although a small amount of canopy cover was present along most of the downstream site (Figure 3). Most sites had some grass overhanging into the water from the edge of the bank, which provided additional habitat complexity for fish and invertebrates. Only in Riffle Creek were aquatic plants and extensive algal mats observed in the channel (Table 1). We observed tadpoles at every site when it contained water. Although fish were always observed in Riffle Creek and the downstream and over-wide downstream sites in McKibben Ditch, they were never seen at the two most-upstream sites in McKibben Ditch.

Water Chemistry

Physicochemical data for the study sites are summarized in Table 2. Weather conditions in the two study years were quite different and this created observable effects in the streams. The drought conditions of 2007 contrasted with the cooler, wetter conditions seen the previous summer and resulted in higher water temperatures in both McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek during 2007. Dissolved oxygen (DO) concentrations in 2006 at the over-wide upstream and Riffle Creek sites were depressed. An exceptionally high DO concentration in Riffle Creek in 2007 corresponded with low turbidity and shallow water and may have reflected increased primary productivity within the stream as a result of increased light penetration.

Conductivity and pH were similar both years in McKibben Ditch. Marked differences in Riffle Creek in 2006 from the other sites in pH, turbidity, and conductivity likely was indicative of flooding about two weeks earlier. All sites were slightly alkaline both years except that Riffle Creek was slightly acidic in 2006 (Table 2).

Macroinvertebrate Communities

Many kinds of aquatic invertebrates were present in the project area. Table 3 shows the number of different taxa (kinds) of aquatic invertebrates found in the semi-quantitative samples and the qualitative samples as well as the total number of taxa overall at each site. As is typical of any survey of this type, the list of taxa was somewhat different between the semi-quantitative samples and the qualitative samples collected at each site as a result of the complementary sampling techniques used for each type of sample that are intended to find aquatic invertebrates in as many different habitats at each site as possible. If exactly the same taxa had been collected in both the semi-quantitative and qualitative samples, the total number of taxa at each site would simply have been the number of taxa in one kind of sample or the other. If the taxa were totally different in the two kinds of samples, the total number of taxa at each site would have been the sum of the semi-quantitative and qualitative taxa. Instead, the total number of taxa always lies

Table 2. Mean physicochemical measurements collected in conjunction with macroinvertebrate sampling. OW = over-wide

Stream Reach	Temp °C	pH	DO mg/L	DO %	Turbidity NTU	Conduc- tivity µS/cm
2006						
McKibben Ditch Downstream	16.9	7.5	8.0	83	12.7	649
McKibben Ditch OW downstream	17.3	7.3	7.1	74	19.2	587
McKibben Ditch OW upstream	19.0	7.2	3.3	37	16.8	616
McKibben Ditch Upstream	28.1	7.6	6.7	87	14.6	610
Riffle Creek	24.9	6.7	4.0	48	50.5	347
2007						
McKibben Ditch Downstream	18.8	7.4	6.4	67	137.5	675
McKibben Ditch OW downstream	20.5	7.7	7.3	81	74.0	555
McKibben Ditch OW upstream	No	water				
McKibben Ditch Upstream	No	water				
Riffle Creek	28.9	8.0	12.3	163	28.0	614

somewhere between those two extremes.

Very similar numbers of taxa were found in the samples from the two replicate (adjacent) stream reaches (A and B) at McKibben Ditch “downstream” in 2006 (36 and 38 taxa) and 2007 (47 and 48 taxa), and “over-wide downstream” in 2007 (40 and 41 taxa). Riffle Creek revealed the fewest taxa both years, and the numbers there were nearly identical both within and between years (31 and 33 taxa in 2006, 30 and 31 taxa in 2007). The remaining sample pairs (upstream, over-wide upstream, and over-wide downstream), all in 2006, showed considerable disparity in the total number of taxa (Table 3).

The sites possessing the highest taxonomic richness were not the same in 2006 and 2007. In 2006, the over-wide upstream site had the highest mean taxonomic richness whereas in 2007, the downstream site had the highest richness. Riffle Creek had the lowest richness both years, and the upstream site, which had no water in 2007, had a richness similarly low to that of Riffle Creek in 2006 (Table 3).

The total number of taxa in each replicate (Table 3) is presented graphically in Figure 5. It is apparent that in 2006 the number of taxa collected varied considerably between replicates A and B at the three upstream-most sites in McKibben Ditch, whereas the replicates yielded very similar numbers of taxa at the downstream-most McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek sites. In 2007 the number of taxa differed only by one between replicates at all three sites sampled. The difference between replicates in actual taxa collected varied much more than that (Appendix C).

Table 3. Taxonomic richness (number of different kinds) of aquatic invertebrates in the semi-quantitative (Quant.) and qualitative (Qual.) samples collected in each stream segment. All sites are in McKibben Ditch except those labeled Riffle (Creek). Total number of taxa is less than the sum of semi-quantitative and qualitative taxa because some taxa were found in both samples. Abbreviations: OW = segments destined for over-wide ditch construction, Up = upstream, Dn = downstream. Refer to Figures 1 and 2.

	2006										2007					
	Up	Up	OW	OW	OW	OW	Dn	Dn	Riffle	Riffle	OW	OW	Dn	Dn	Riffle	Riffle
	A6	B6	A6	B6	A6	B6	A6	B6	A6	B6	A7	B7	A7	B7	A7	B7
Quant.	15	21	36	23	22	38	28	22	23	17	36	39	35	35	25	27
Qual.	27	33	29	28	22	19	19	28	18	22	18	14	29	33	18	16
Total	30	38	47	37	29	46	36	38	31	33	41	40	47	48	30	31
Mean Total	34.0		42.0		37.5		37.0		32.0		40.5		47.5		30.5	

The proportions of the major aquatic invertebrate groups present in the semi-quantitative samples showed some commonalities across sites both years (Table 4). Figure 6 presents the average contributions of six groups. Chironomid midges (fly family Chironomidae) contributed over 10% of the invertebrates in almost every sample both years. In each of the three samples in which they contributed less than 10%, the paired replicate sample for that site revealed a high proportion: over-wide upstream (20% and 3%, 2006), over-wide downstream (34% and 8%, 2006), and downstream (8% and 41%, 2007). The remaining sites, with higher contributions of midges, revealed relatively consistent proportions between replicates A and B. Midges comprised almost all of the aquatic invertebrates in Riffle Creek in 2007, contributing an average of 87% of all individuals collected; in 2006 the average contribution was only 33% (Table 4).

Pill clams and fingernail clams (very small clams only distantly related to the large, more-familiar mussels) also contributed a large proportion of the total individuals at most sites both years. Clams made a larger contribution than the midges at the upstream and downstream sites in 2006 and were twice as abundant as midges at the downstream site in 2007. By contrast, the clams were almost completely absent ($\leq 0.3\%$) from Riffle Creek both years (Table 4, Figure 6).

Oligochaete worms comprised a third group that contributed over 10% of the total organisms, and they contributed up to 64% at several sites (8 of 10 samples) in 2006, but their contribution was $< 5\%$ in all samples collected in 2007. They were the most abundant group (average 61%) in Riffle Creek in 2006 but contributed only 4% in 2007 (Table 4). The other two groups that contributed over 10% of the individuals in at least a third of all samples were the beetles and snails. Beetles contributed 33% of all individuals at the over-wide downstream site in 2007, 14.5% downstream in 2006 and 10.5% downstream in 2007 but otherwise were minor contributors. None were collected at the upstream site in 2006, and very few ($< 0.5\%$) were collected in Riffle Creek either year. Snails contributed more than 10% (up to 34%) of individuals in three of four samples in 2006 at the upstream and over-wide upstream sites, and in three of four samples from the over-wide downstream and downstream sites (up to 23%) in

Figure 5. Total number of taxa (kinds) of aquatic invertebrates found in each replicate sample at each site in 2006 and 2007

2007. Snails were nearly absent from the semi-quantitative samples ($\leq 0.4\%$) from Riffle Creek both years (Table 4, Figure 6).

True bugs (such as water striders, water boatmen, backswimmers, water bugs; insect Order Hemiptera) generally comprised a minor group, but they contributed 10% of the individuals in one of the two replicates at both the upstream site in 2006 and Riffle Creek in 2007 (Table 3). “EPT insects” is a category that includes all mayflies (Ephemeroptera), stoneflies (Plecoptera) and caddisflies (Trichoptera). No stoneflies were found. Very few mayflies or caddisflies were found upstream in 2006 ($< 0.1\%$ in 2006, dry in 2007); none were found in Riffle Creek in 2006 and very few there in 2007 (0.3%). However, small mayflies of the genus *Paracloeodes* (Family Baetidae) were relatively abundant in one of the two samples at the over-wide downstream site in 2006, comprising 33% of all individuals, while making up only 6% in the other sample. This was a result of the extremely heterogeneous nature of the habitats throughout the over-wide downstream site that were noted above in the description of the study area.

The overall similarity of the samples – and the sites – to each other is best compared on the basis of both the invertebrate taxa present and their proportional contributions to the total invertebrate community. Therefore, the percent similarities of all possible pair-wise combinations of replicate samples were computed (Krebs 1999). As expected if the sampling methodology and effort were consistent, the greatest pair-wise similarities were almost all between replicates collected at the same site in a given year (on the same day), with similarities ranging from 63% to 76% (Table 5). Only at the over-wide upstream and over-wide downstream sites in 2006 was this not the case, and as noted above, the highly variable habitat throughout the over-wide downstream site would be expected to yield an inconsistent community. According to percent similarities, replicate A of the downstream site in 2006 revealed a 60% or higher

Table 4. Proportional contributions of major taxonomic groups at each site each year. (6=2006, 7=2007. All sites are in McKibben Ditch except those labeled Riffle (Creek). Abbreviations: OW = segments destined for over-wide ditch construction, Up = upstream, Dn = downstream (refer to figures 1 and 2); EPT = mayflies+stoneflies+caddisflies. Shaded numbers contributed 10.0% or more of the total.

	Up A6	Up B6	OW Up A6	OW Up B6	OW Dn A6	OW Dn B6	Dn A6	Dn B6	Riffle A6	Riffle B6	OW Dn A7	OW Dn B7	Dn A7	Dn B7	Riffle A7	Riffle B7
Miscellaneous	0.013	0.043	0.106	0.055	<0.001	0.053	0.003	0.005	0.026	0.025	0.012	0.027	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.002
Oligochaete worms	0.331	0.160	0.269	0.399	0.091	0.491	0.105	0.063	0.587	0.642	0.015	0.023	0.012	0.028	0.029	0.047
EPT insects	0.000	0.009	0.013	0.022	0.330	0.057	0.062	0.063	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.009	0.012	0.011	0.003	0.003
Dragonflies, damselflies, alderflies	0.000	0.000	0.007	0.002	<0.001	0.011	<0.001	0.000	0.001	0.013	0.005	0.005	0.007	0.002	0.001	<0.001
True bugs	0.105	0.089	0.048	0.058	0.000	0.020	0.015	0.034	0.017	0.017	0.008	0.023	0.001	0.003	0.050	0.101
Beetles	0.000	0.000	0.006	0.016	0.084	0.054	0.159	0.131	0.005	0.000	0.325	0.335	0.110	0.100	0.006	0.003
Chironomid midges	0.153	0.170	0.201	0.030	0.344	0.080	0.170	0.359	0.356	0.302	0.201	0.208	0.086	0.408	0.901	0.837
Non-Chironomid flies	0.000	0.005	0.001	0.002	0.098	0.003	0.008	0.000	0.009	0.000	0.009	0.066	0.001	0.004	0.000	0.000
Snails	0.040	0.180	0.140	0.396	0.033	0.076	0.038	0.049	0.000	0.001	0.232	0.135	0.142	0.069	0.004	0.004
Pill and Fingernail Clams	0.358	0.344	0.210	0.019	0.019	0.154	0.440	0.294	0.000	0.001	0.165	0.171	0.627	0.371	0.003	0.002

Figure 6. Average contributions of major groups of aquatic macroinvertebrates at each ditch and stream site in 2006 and 2007. Proportions for replicates A and B at each site (Table 4) were averaged. Upstream and Over-wide Upstream were dry in 2007 and therefore were not sampled that year. “Miscellaneous” includes several groups that are presented separately in Table 4.

similarity to its replicate and also to both replicates at that site in 2007. The Riffle Creek samples were the most similar pairs among all sites both years but were highly dissimilar between years. The Riffle Creek samples were also highly dissimilar to almost all other samples, especially in 2007.

Dendrograms produced by means of cluster analysis are another means of revealing which samples were more similar to each other than to the other samples on the basis of their invertebrate community composition. We performed cluster analysis using several distance measures (Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, Pearson correlation), and linkage methods (single, average, complete, median, centroid) in various combinations (Minitab 2000).

All resulting dendrograms were similar, and two are compared in figures 7 and 8. In both cases, five major clusters consisting of as many as five samples are present. As also revealed by the similarity matrix (Table 5), several pairs of replicate samples collected on the same day at the same site possessed the greatest similarity among sites. In the first dendrogram (average linkage, squared Euclidean distances; Figure 7) these were upstream (McKibben Ditch) and Riffle Creek in 2006 and over-wide downstream and Riffle Creek in 2007. In the second dendrogram (complete linkage, Manhattan distances; Figure 8) these were upstream, downstream, and Riffle Creek in 2006, and over-wide downstream, downstream and Riffle Creek in 2007. In the second dendrogram, all of the 2007 samples were isolated in different clusters (D and E) from the 2006 samples (clusters A-C), whereas there was some intermixing of years in the first dendrogram. These clustering patterns indicate that our sampling technique and effort were similar between replicates at each site and that the macroinvertebrate community was relatively homogeneous in the two contiguous replicate stream reaches at each site. Despite a visually very heterogeneous habitat throughout the over-wide downstream site, the invertebrate community composition was sufficiently similar overall there that the two replicates showed the most affinity for each other in 2007; that was not the case in 2006, in which the A replicate was not very similar to any other samples according to one clustering approach (cluster A in Figure 7) and was more similar to the two upstream replicates than to its own replicate according to the other approach (cluster A in Figure 8). Riffle Creek was similar to sites in McKibben Ditch in 2006 (cluster D, Figure 7; cluster B, Figure 8) but was distinct from all McKibben Ditch sites in 2007 (cluster E, figures 7 and 8).

Discussion

Our findings regarding habitat characteristics of the stream or ditch channels, banks, and riparian zones provide a context for understanding the composition and quality of the aquatic macroinvertebrate communities at each study site. Our stream and ditch segments did not qualify as Primary Headwater Habitat because, by definition (OEPA 2002), a primary headwater stream has pool depths no greater than 40 cm and a drainage area of one square mile or less. The watershed areas above all of our sites were larger than one square mile, and maximum pool depths (although pools were poorly developed at most sites) were at least 50 cm at every site in 2006 except the over-wide downstream site (37 cm). By contrast, because of the drought during our sampling in 2007, all of our sites were less than 40 cm deep except downstream (41 cm), and the two most-upstream McKibben Ditch sites had no standing water. As the ditch construction

Table 5. Percent similarity of each pairwise comparison of sites in McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek based on proportional contributions of all taxa in the semi-quantitative samples. Similarities of less than 15% have a light shading; similarities of more than 60% have a dark shading.

	2006										2007					
	Up B	OW Up A	OW Up B	OW Dn A	OW Dn B	Dn A	Dn B	Rf A	Rf B	OW Dn A	OW Dn B	Dn A	Dn B	Rf A	Rf B	
2006																
Up A	63.6	60.6	45.3	16.2	39.3	36.3	46.6	42.1	40.4	10.5	9.6	30.0	25.0	10.1	8.9	
Up B		49.3	38.8	20.7	29.3	37.5	46.2	24.2	20.1	10.9	10.0	27.4	24.7	15.0	19.0	
OW Up A			46.5	14.5	42.6	36.3	36.4	32.5	28.8	12.3	9.5	29.7	37.2	5.3	6.7	
OW Up B				14.9	55.5	16.9	15.0	42.4	41.5	7.4	8.0	5.0	7.0	3.6	5.5	
OW Dn A					30.8	37.0	40.3	20.3	11.1	25.7	22.1	14.5	20.4	18.9	10.4	
OW Dn B						42.3	29.0	55.9	52.2	33.7	30.3	26.9	30.0	7.9	6.5	
Dn A							63.6	18.6	13.0	47.6	47.6	61.5	59.9	7.8	8.4	
Dn B								16.8	8.9	36.7	31.6	45.4	43.5	24.0	21.2	
Rf A									75.7	16.6	15.8	6.5	13.8	11.1	16.8	
Rf B										6.2	6.9	3.0	6.0	15.4	14.7	
2007																
OW Dn A											69.8	49.8	46.7	9.1	10.2	
OW Dn B													45.5	46.6	10.5	19.3
Dn A														63.5	5.1	4.3
Dn B															9.9	11.5
Rf A																71.0

project proceeds, continuous monitoring of the surface hydrology of McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek is advisable because that information would be extremely useful in interpreting results of habitat and biological assessments that might be scheduled a year or two in the future, following completion of construction. For example, a different macroinvertebrate community is expected in a small stream that “dries up” most summers than in one with continuous, uninterrupted surface flow. The HHEI evaluations provided information on a large variety of habitat characteristics that will be useful for observing modifications created by ditch construction and maintenance as well as subsequent changes brought about naturally by the stream hydrology.

Figure 7. Cluster dendrogram of all semi-quantitative samples collected in McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek in 2006 and 2007, derived from average linkage of squared Euclidean distances based on percentages of taxa

Figure 8. Cluster dendrogram of all semi-quantitative samples collected in McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek in 2006 and 2007, derived from complete linkage of Manhattan distances based on percentages of taxa

Stone *et al.* (2005) found that in-stream habitat was the primary factor influencing the quality of the aquatic macroinvertebrate community of agricultural “drainage ditches” in southern Illinois. The ditches in their study harbored “abundant macroinvertebrates that are typical of degraded conditions [but that] can reflect gradients of conditions in and around these streams.” The present assessment of McKibben Ditch and Riffle Creek revealed (especially Figure 6) a preponderance of macroinvertebrates that are highly tolerant of degraded stream habitat, including fingernail clams, oligochaete worms, and snails. Those groups that are especially indicative of good habitat conditions, the mayflies, stoneflies, and caddisflies (OEPA 1987, 2002), were nearly absent from all of our sites.

Ohio EPA recently published a TMDL (Total Maximum Daily Load) report for the Olentangy River Watershed (OEPA 2007). That report makes no mention of McKibben Ditch but it does include data on Riffle Creek. Ohio EPA has sampled Riffle Creek near Marion-Edison Road a short distance below its confluence with an eastern branch of nearly equal length. At that location, Riffle Creek is a second-order stream with a drainage area of 10.2 square miles and it has been designated as Modified Warmwater Habitat (MWH) because that stream segment is under long-term ditch maintenance, while several miles downstream it is classified as Warm Water Habitat (WWH). The TMDL report states (p. 40):

Riffle Creek, a tributary to Grave Creek, was channelized in 1946. Riffle Creek is not currently maintained by the county, but stream’s naturally low-gradient and landowner maintenance has slowed its recovery. Riffle Creek is designated WWH from its mouth to RM 4.0, near Marion-Edison Road. The remaining portion is MWH. Riffle Creek is in non-attainment of MWH at RM 4.6, and partial attainment of WWH at RM 0.1.

QHEI results of Riffle Creek are good in the downstream WWH segment, and poor in the upstream MWH segment. It is not surprising the upstream segment, with a total QHEI score of 29.0, is not attaining its aquatic life use. Habitat conditions degraded to such an extent simply cannot support a healthy aquatic community. The lower segment received a total QHEI score of 75.0, which significantly exceeds its target and absent of other impacts should support an aquatic community consistent with its use. The partial attainment of this segment could therefore be a result of pollutant loading from upstream.

QHEI scores for our sites were to be determined by the separate fish assessment team from The Ohio State University and were not available for this report. However, our HHEI (Headwater Habitat Evaluation Index) scores and accompanying habitat characteristics (Table 1), most of which are components of the QHEI (Rankin 1989), do indicate highly degraded stream habitat conditions at all sites.

In Riffle Creek at the Marion-Edison Road site (RM 4.40), Ohio EPA performed a qualitative invertebrate community assessment in September 2003 (OEPA 2005). By comparison using the same taxonomic levels as in our present study, Ohio EPA reported 47 macroinvertebrate taxa as compared to 31 to 33 taxa in each of the replicate samples and cumulatively 48 taxa in 2006 and 39 taxa in 2007 from our site in Riffle Creek 0.8 mile upstream. However, our samples from the summers of 2006 and 2007 combined shared only 22 taxa with the taxa listed by Ohio EPA at their more-downstream site. They reported 9 “qualitative EPT” taxa, which are the insect orders most sensitive over-all to stream habitat degradation, whereas we found only one EPT taxon (a mayfly) at our site in 2006 and 4 EPT taxa (3 mayflies and 1 caddisfly) in 2007. Even though the Ohio EPA site and our site were only

0.8 mile apart, the watershed area at the Ohio EPA site is more than twice as large and might contribute to stream habitat conditions sufficiently different from those at our site to account for some of the differences in the biota. As shown in our data for samples collected only one year apart, some of the differences between the two studies could also be a result simply of sampling in different years. Because Ohio EPA has not sampled McKibben Ditch, no comparisons can be made for that stream.

The objectives of the present study included establishing a set of baseline data for the stream habitat and macroinvertebrate communities in order to detect and quantify changes following over-wide ditch construction. The study was related only indirectly to TMDLs for the Olentangy River and was not intended to calculate macroinvertebrate index scores for each of the sampling sites. Now that baseline conditions are known, we recommend that a follow-up study be carried out as soon as practical following installation of the over-wide ditch in order to complete the original goals of this study.

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Appendix A. Ohio EPA Primary Headwater Habitat Evaluation Form (HHEI)

Primary Headwater Habitat Evaluation Form

HHEI Score (sum of metrics 1, 2, 3) :

SITE NAME/LOCATION _____
 _____ SITE NUMBER _____ RIVER BASIN _____ DRAINAGE AREA (mi²) _____
 LENGTH OF STREAM REACH (ft) _____ LAT. _____ LONG. _____ RIVER CODE _____ RIVER MILE _____
 DATE _____ SCORER _____ COMMENTS _____

NOTE: Complete All Items On This Form - Refer to "Field Evaluation Manual for Ohio's PWH Streams" for Instructions

STREAM CHANNEL NONE / NATURAL CHANNEL RECOVERED RECOVERING RECENT OR NO RECOVERY

MODIFICATIONS:

<p>1. SUBSTRATE (Estimate percent of every type of substrate present. Check <u>ONLY two</u> predominant substrate TYPE boxes (Max of 32). Add total number of significant substrate types found (Max of 8). Final metric score is sum of boxes A & B.)</p> <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 15%;">TYPE</th> <th style="width: 35%;">PERCENT</th> <th style="width: 15%;">TYPE</th> <th style="width: 35%;">PERCENT</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> BLDR SLABS [16 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> SILT [3 pt]</td> <td>_____</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> BOULDER (>256 mm) [16 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> LEAF PACK/WOODY DEBRIS [3 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> BEDROCK [16 pt]</td> <td>_____</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> FINE DETRITUS [3 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> COBBLE (65-256 mm) [12 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> CLAY or HARDPAN [0 pt]</td> <td>_____</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> GRAVEL (2-64 mm) [9 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> MUCK [0 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> SAND (<2 mm) [6 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> ARTIFICIAL [3 pts]</td> <td>_____</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p style="text-align: center;">Total of Percentages of Bldr Slabs, Boulder, Cobble, Bedrock (A) <input style="width: 40px;" type="text"/> (B) <input style="width: 40px;" type="text"/></p> <p>SCORE OF TWO MOST PREDOMINATE SUBSTRATE TYPES: TOTAL NUMBER OF SUBSTRATE TYPES:</p>	TYPE	PERCENT	TYPE	PERCENT	<input type="checkbox"/> BLDR SLABS [16 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> SILT [3 pt]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> BOULDER (>256 mm) [16 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> LEAF PACK/WOODY DEBRIS [3 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> BEDROCK [16 pt]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> FINE DETRITUS [3 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> COBBLE (65-256 mm) [12 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> CLAY or HARDPAN [0 pt]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> GRAVEL (2-64 mm) [9 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> MUCK [0 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> SAND (<2 mm) [6 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> ARTIFICIAL [3 pts]	_____	<p>HHEI Metric Points</p> <p>Substrate Max = 40</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; width: 40px; height: 40px; margin: 0 auto;"></div> <p>A + B</p> <hr/> <p>Pool Depth Max = 30</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; width: 40px; height: 40px; margin: 0 auto;"></div> <hr/> <p>Bankfull Width Max=30</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; width: 40px; height: 40px; margin: 0 auto;"></div>
TYPE	PERCENT	TYPE	PERCENT																										
<input type="checkbox"/> BLDR SLABS [16 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> SILT [3 pt]	_____																										
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<input type="checkbox"/> SAND (<2 mm) [6 pts]	_____	<input type="checkbox"/> ARTIFICIAL [3 pts]	_____																										
<p>2. Maximum Pool Depth (Measure the maximum pool depth within the 61 meter (200 ft) evaluation reach at the time of evaluation. Avoid plunge pools from road culverts or storm water pipes) (Check <u>ONLY one</u> box):</p> <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 30 centimeters [20 pts]</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 5 cm - 10 cm [15 pts]</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 22.5 - 30 cm [30 pts]</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> < 5 cm [5 pts]</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 10 - 22.5 cm [25 pts]</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> NO WATER OR MOIST CHANNEL [0 pts]</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>COMMENTS _____ MAXIMUM POOL DEPTH (centimeters): <input style="width: 60px;" type="text"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/> > 30 centimeters [20 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> > 5 cm - 10 cm [15 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> > 22.5 - 30 cm [30 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> < 5 cm [5 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> > 10 - 22.5 cm [25 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> NO WATER OR MOIST CHANNEL [0 pts]																							
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<p>3. BANK FULL WIDTH (Measured as the average of 3-4 measurements) (Check <u>ONLY one</u> box):</p> <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 4.0 meters (> 13') [30 pts]</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 1.0 m - 1.5 m (> 3' 3" - 4' 8") [15 pts]</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 3.0 m - 4.0 m (> 9' 7" - 13') [25 pts]</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> ≤ 1.0 m (≤ 3' 3") [5 pts]</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> > 1.5 m - 3.0 m (> 9' 7" - 4' 8") [20 pts]</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>COMMENTS _____ AVERAGE BANKFULL WIDTH (meters) <input style="width: 60px;" type="text"/></p>	<input type="checkbox"/> > 4.0 meters (> 13') [30 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> > 1.0 m - 1.5 m (> 3' 3" - 4' 8") [15 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> > 3.0 m - 4.0 m (> 9' 7" - 13') [25 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> ≤ 1.0 m (≤ 3' 3") [5 pts]	<input type="checkbox"/> > 1.5 m - 3.0 m (> 9' 7" - 4' 8") [20 pts]																								
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This information must also be completed

RIPARIAN ZONE AND FLOODPLAIN QUALITY ΔNOTE: River Left (L) and Right (R) as looking downstream:Δ

RIPARIAN WIDTH		FLOODPLAIN QUALITY			
L	R	L	R	L	R
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wide >10m		Mature Forest, Wetland		Conservation Tillage	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Moderate 5-10m		Immature Forest, Shrub or Old Field		Urban or Industrial	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Narrow <5m		Residential, Park, New Field		Open Pasture, Row Crop	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
None		Fenced Pasture		Mining or Construction	

COMMENTS _____

FLOW REGIME (At Time of Evaluation) (Check ONLY one box):

<input type="checkbox"/> Stream Flowing	<input type="checkbox"/> Moist Channel, isolated pools, no flow (Intermittent)
<input type="checkbox"/> Subsurface flow with isolated pools (Interstitial)	<input type="checkbox"/> Dry channel, no water (Ephemeral)

COMMENTS _____

SINUOSITY (Number of bends per 61 m (200 ft) of channel) (Check ONLY one box):

<input type="checkbox"/> None	<input type="checkbox"/> 1.0	<input type="checkbox"/> 2.0	<input type="checkbox"/> 3.0
<input type="checkbox"/> 0.5	<input type="checkbox"/> 1.5	<input type="checkbox"/> 2.5	<input type="checkbox"/> >3

STREAM GRADIENT ESTIMATE

<input type="checkbox"/> Flat (0.5 ft/100 ft)	<input type="checkbox"/> Flat to Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate (2 ft/100 ft)	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate to Severe	<input type="checkbox"/> Severe (10 ft/100 ft)
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ADDITIONAL STREAM INFORMATION (This Information Must Also be Completed):

QHEI PERFORMED? - Yes No QHEI Score _____ (If Yes, Attach Completed QHEI Form)

DOWNSTREAM DESIGNATED USE(S)

WWH Name: _____ Distance from Evaluated Stream _____
 CWH Name: _____ Distance from Evaluated Stream _____
 EWH Name: _____ Distance from Evaluated Stream _____

MAPPING: ATTACH COPIES OF MAPS, INCLUDING THE ENTIRE WATERSHED AREA. CLEARLY MARK THE SITE LOCATION

USGS Quadrangle Name: _____ NRCS Soil Map Page: _____ NRCS Soil Map Stream Order _____

County: _____ Township / City: _____

MISCELLANEOUS

Base Flow Conditions? (Y/N): _____ Date of last precipitation: _____ Quantity: _____

Photograph Information: _____

Elevated Turbidity? (Y/N): _____ Canopy (% open): _____

Were samples collected for water chemistry? (Y/N): _____ (Note lab sample no. or id. and attach results) Lab Number: _____

Field Measures: Temp (°C) _____ Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l) _____ pH (S.U.) _____ Conductivity (µmhos/cm) _____

Is the sampling reach representative of the stream (Y/N) _____ If not, please explain: _____

Additional comments/description of pollution impacts: _____

BIOTIC EVALUATION

Performed? (Y/N): _____ (If Yes, Record all observations. Voucher collections optional. NOTE: all voucher samples must be labeled with the site ID number. Include appropriate field data sheets from the Primary Headwater Habitat Assessment Manual)

Fish Observed? (Y/N) _____ Voucher? (Y/N) _____ Salamanders Observed? (Y/N) _____ Voucher? (Y/N) _____
Frogs or Tadpoles Observed? (Y/N) _____ Voucher? (Y/N) _____ Aquatic Macroinvertebrates Observed? (Y/N) _____ Voucher? (Y/N) _____

Comments Regarding Biology: _____

DRAWING AND NARRATIVE DESCRIPTION OF STREAM REACH (This must be completed):

Include important landmarks and other features of interest for site evaluation and a narrative description of the stream's location

FLOW →

Appendix B. Flag locations used to locate invertebrate sampling sites

Stream Reach		N Latitude	W Longitude
McKibben Ditch Downstream	lower limit	40°32.100'	83°59.688'
	middle	40°32.114'	83°59.676'
	upper limit	40°32.128'	83°59.662'
McKibben Ditch Over-wide Downstream	lower limit	40°32.161'	82°59.594'
	middle	40°32.175'	82°59.577'
	upper limit	40°32.184'	82°59.560'
McKibben Ditch Over-wide Upstream	lower limit	40°32.997'	82°58.729'
	middle	40°33.007'	82°58.706'
	upper limit	40°33.116'	82°58.692'
McKibben Ditch Upstream	lower limit	40°33.043'	82°58.586'
	middle	40°33.057'	82°58.576'
	upper limit	40°33.069'	82°58.563'
Riffle Creek	lower limit	40°34.026'	83°02.711'
	middle	40°34.038'	83°02.726'
	upper limit	40°34.049'	83°02.741'

Appendix C

Number of each invertebrate taxon identified in the semi-quantitative "dip-net" samples collected in July 2006 and July 2007. All sampling sites (reaches A and B) were in McKibben Ditch except those designated as Riffle Creek ("Riffle"). "OW" refers to stream reaches that were to be modified in an "over-wide" ditch architecture (see figures 1 and 2). "+" indicates presence in qualitative samples.

		2006									
Taxon	Site	Up A	Up B	OW Up A	OW Up B	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Riffle A	Riffle B
Cnidaria											
Hydridae (hydra)		+							8	+	16 +
Turbellaria (flatworm)											
									13 +	+	16 +
Oligochaeta (segmented worm)											
Tubificidae		1568 +	544 +	1414 +	864 +	208 +	1328 +	656 +	209 +	2201 +	888 +
Lumbriculidae				3			17		+		2
Hirudinea (leech)											
<i>Erpobdella punctata</i>			2		+				+		
<i>Haemopsis sp.</i>						+					
<i>Helobdella elongata</i>				3							1
<i>Helobdella papillata</i>				+						+	
<i>Helobdella stagnalis</i>									+	49 +	1
<i>Placobdella multilineata</i>						1	3		16 +	16	
Branchiopoda											
Conchostraca (clam shrimp)											
<i>Eulimnadia sp.</i>											+
Ostracoda (seed shrimp)		64 +	128 +		20		1				16
Isopoda (sow bug)											
Asellidae											
<i>Caecidotea sp.</i>		+	17 +	543 +	100 +		120				
Amphipoda (sideswimmer)											
Crangonictidae											
<i>Crangonyx sp.</i>					+						
Hyalalleidae											
<i>Hyalella sp.</i>		+	+					16 +	+		
Decapoda (crayfish)											
Cambaridae											
				1 +				1	1 +		
Hydrachnida (water mite)											
				10 +	+						
Ephemeroptera (mayfly)											
Baetidae											
<i>Paracloeodes sp.</i>		+	32 +	41 +	48 +	737 +	148 +	353 +	192 +	+	+
<i>Callibaetis sp.</i>				1							
Caenidae											
<i>Caenis sp.</i>							1	16	16		
Ephemeridae											
<i>Hexagenia sp.</i>				16			8				
Heptageniidae											
<i>Stenacron sp.</i>									+		
<i>Stenonema sp.</i>									+		
Odonata (dragonfly)											
Aeshnidae											
<i>Boyeria sp.</i>						1 +	1	+	+	+	
<i>Anax sp.</i>				+							+
Calopterygidae											
<i>Calopteryx sp.</i>						+					
Cocnagrionidae											
<i>Argia sp.</i>								+			
<i>Inallagma sp.</i>		+	+	39 +	4 +		29		+	1 +	18 +
Corduliidae											

		2006									
Taxon	Site	Up A	Up B	OW Up A	OW Up B	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Riffle A	Riffle B
<i>Somatochlora sp.</i>		+	+			+	1				+
Gomphidae										1	
Lestidae											
<i>Lestes sp.</i>				+	+						
Libellulidae											
<i>Plathemis sp.</i>								1			
Lepidoptera											
Pyrilidae											
<i>Acentria sp.</i>										1	
Hemiptera (true bug)											
Belostomatidae											
<i>Belostoma sp.</i>		+		1 +	+		1			+	+
Corixidae (water boatman)				1							
Corixini											
<i>Palmacorixa sp.</i>			+	+			55				+
<i>Sigara sp.</i>		496 +		251	126 +		+	96	112 +		
<i>Trichocortixa sp.</i>			304					+		64 +	23
Gerridae											
<i>Trepobates sp.</i>										+	
Notonectidae (backswimmer)											
<i>Notonecta sp.</i>		+	+	+	+						+
Megaloptera											
Corydalidae (helgrammite)											
<i>Chauliodes sp.</i>								+			
Sialidae											
<i>Sialis sp.</i>											
Trichoptera (caddisfly)											
Hydropsychidae											
<i>Cheumatopsyche sp.</i>				8		16 +	+				
<i>Hydropsyche sp.</i>						+					
Hydroptilidae											
Leptoceridae											
<i>Oecetis sp.</i>								17			
Coloptera (beetle)											
Dytiscidae											
<i>Hydroporus sp.</i>				+	+		+				
<i>Laccophilus sp.</i>			+	14	20 +						
<i>Liodessus sp.</i>					+						
<i>Ilybius sp.</i>					+						
<i>Oreodytes sp.</i>				6							
<i>Thermonectus sp.?</i>											
Elmidae (riffle beetle)											
<i>Dubiraphia sp.</i>						144 +	123 +	913 +	416 +		
<i>Stenelmis sp.</i>				1	2	32 +	2	80	16		
Gyrinidae											
<i>Gyrinus sp.</i>						+		1 +	+		+
Halplidae											
<i>Peltodytes sp.</i>			+	9 +	8 +	16 +	22 +	+	+	1	+
Hydrophilidae											
<i>Berosus sp.</i>										16 +	+
<i>Enochrus sp.</i>								+			
<i>Helophorus sp.</i>				+	4		1		+		
<i>Hydrochara sp.</i>				1							
<i>Hydrophilus sp.</i>											
<i>Tropisternus sp.</i>		+	+								+
Lampyridae					+						

		2006									
Taxon	Site	Up A	Up B	OW Up A	OW Up B	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Rifle A	Rifle B
Scirtidae											
<i>Prionocyphon sp.</i>											
Diptera (true fly)											
Ceratopogonidae (no-see-um)											
<i>Atrichopogon sp.</i>							1				
<i>Bezzia or Palpomyia sp.</i>							2	16			+
Chironomidae (midge)											
Tribe Chironomini											
<i>Apedilum sp.</i>								64			
<i>Chironomus sp.</i>		93	16 +	796	12 +		8		33	100	
<i>Cryptochironomus sp.</i>								96		92	91 +
<i>Cryptotendipes sp.</i>							8		66	17	
<i>Dicrotendipes sp.</i>						+				135	
<i>Endochironomus sp.</i>			+								
<i>Goeldichironomus sp.</i>					6					50	
<i>Microtendipes sp.</i>			32								
<i>Parachironomus sp.</i>								16 +			8
<i>Paralauterborniella sp.</i>								64			
<i>Paratendipes sp.</i>		75 +	128 +	12 +	+						
<i>Phaenopsectra sp.</i>					6						
<i>Polypedilum sp.</i>		56 +	64 +	+	+	320 +	72	64	157	66	8
<i>Pseudochironomus sp.</i>			+			16				16	
<i>Stichtochironomus sp.</i>											
Tribe Tanytarsini											
<i>Cladotanytarsus sp.</i>											
<i>Paratanytarsus sp.</i>		+	51 +	49		160 +	59 +	456	272 +	162	+
<i>Rheotanytarsus sp.</i>											
<i>Tanytarsus sp.</i>		212 +	171 +	91	12 +	112	8	156 +	488	34	
<i>Zavrelia sp.</i>			34								
Subfamily Orthoclaadiinae											
<i>Corynoneura sp.</i>				17 +		32 +	+				
<i>Cricotopus sp.</i>							8		+		
<i>Euryhopsis sp.</i>								32			
<i>Nanocladius sp.</i>						64 +				+	+
<i>Orthocladus sp.</i>		+	16 +						48 +		
<i>Parakiefferiella sp.</i>								48 +			
<i>Smittia sp.</i>			+								
Subfamily Tanypodinae											
<i>Clinotanypus sp.</i>		+		5					+	17	3
<i>Krenopelopia sp.</i>					6					17	
<i>Labrundinia sp.</i>			+								
<i>Natarsia sp.</i>			+	2				64	17		
<i>Pentaneura sp.</i>			16 +	7 +		16	8		17		
<i>Psectrotanypus sp.</i>				21							
<i>Procladius sp.</i>		237 +	16 +	45 +	6	32	32		52 +	444 +	274 +
<i>Reomyia sp.</i>		17									
<i>Tanypus sp.</i>		17 +									34
<i>Thienemannimyia grp.</i>		+	32 +	16 +	16 +	32 +	16 +	2 +		220 +	
<i>Zavrelimyia sp.</i>		17									
Culicidae (mosquito)											
<i>Aedes sp.</i>			+								
<i>Anopheles sp.</i>			+	+	4 +		3				
<i>Culex sp.</i>					+						
Dixidae											
<i>Dixella sp.</i>				2 +			1				
Empididae											

		2006											
Taxon	Site	Up A	Up B	OW Up A	OW Up B	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Riffle A	Riffle B		
<i>Hemerodromia sp.</i>							+						
<i>Ramphomyia sp.</i>								16					
Ephydriidae (not keyed)							2						
Sciomyzidae				1									
Simuliidae (black fly)													
<i>Ectemnia sp. ?</i>						+							
<i>Simulium sp.</i>			16	+		224		16			32 +		
Stratiomyidae													
<i>Nemotelus sp. ?</i>													
<i>Ondontomyia sp.</i>													
<i>Stratiomys sp.</i>													
Tipulidae (cranefly)													
<i>Tipula sp.</i>													
Gastropoda (snail)													
Ancylidae (limpet)													
<i>Ferrissia sp.</i>						32				+			
Lymnaeidae (pond snail)													
<i>Fossaria sp.</i>		18 +	+	381 +	+								+
<i>Stagnicola sp.</i>		+		+	86 +		+	+					
Physidae (pouch snail)													
<i>Physella sp.</i>		65 +	210 +	280 +	247 +			126 +			+		1 +
Planorbidae (ram's-horn snail)													
<i>Helisoma sp.</i>		109 +	400 +	76 +	525 +			4 +	+	+	+		+
Pleuroceridae (riffle snail)													
<i>Elimia sp.</i>						43 +	78 +	239	162 +				
Bivalvia (clam, mussel)													
Sphaeriidae (fingernail clam)													
<i>Musculium sp.</i>													
<i>Pisidium sp.</i>		1699 +	1168 +	1109 +	10	1 +	48	1296 +	944 +				2
<i>Sphaerium sp.</i>		+	+		32	43 +	373 +	1456 +	26 +				1
Total Taxa either quant or qual		15 27	21 33	36 29	23 28	22 22	38 19	28 19	22 28	23 18	17 22		
Total individuals		4743	3397	5273	2164	2282	2739	6251	3294	3750	1387		
Total All Taxa		30	38	47	37	29	46	36	38	31	33		
		2006 total											
		35280											

		2007					
Taxon	Site	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Riffle A	Riffle B
Cnidaria							
Hydridae (hydra)			3				
Turbellaria (flatworm)		10 +	27	+	+	8 +	8 +
Oligochaeta (segmented worm)							
Tubificidae		15 +	17 +	29	74 +	160 +	305
Lumbriculidae		1	12	13	22	69	95
Hirudinea (leech)							
<i>Erpobdella punctata</i>			3	+		3	1
<i>Haemopsis sp.</i>							
<i>Helobdella elongata</i>							
<i>Helobdella papillata</i>							
<i>Helobdella stagnalis</i>		1		3	1 +	21	
<i>Placobdella multilineata</i>				5	11		9
Branchiopoda							
Conchostraca (clam shrimp)							
<i>Eulimnadia sp.</i>							
Ostracoda (seed shrimp)							
Isopoda (sow bug)							
Asellidae							
<i>Caecidotea sp.</i>		1					
Amphipoda (sideswimmer)							
Crangonictidae							
<i>Crangonyx sp.</i>			1				
Hyallelidae							
<i>Hyalella sp.</i>				2 +	+		
Decapoda (crayfish)							
Cambaridae				1 +			
Hydrachnida (water mite)							
Ephemeroptera (mayfly)							
Baetidae							
<i>Paracloodes sp.</i>		2 +			1 +	2	
<i>Callibaetis sp.</i>			1	17 +	+	+	1 +
Caenidae							
<i>Caenis sp.</i>		1			9	25 +	20 +
Ephemeridae							
<i>Hexagenia sp.</i>			1 +	14	4		
Heptageniidae							
<i>Stenacron sp.</i>							
<i>Stenonema sp.</i>				+			
Odonata (dragonfly)							
Aeshnidae							
<i>Boyeria sp.</i>					+	+	
<i>Anax sp.</i>					+		
Calopterygidae							
<i>Calopteryx sp.</i>							
Coenagrionidae							
<i>Argia sp.</i>							
<i>Enallagma sp.</i>		5	3 +	10 +	1 +	+	+
Corduliidae							

		2007					
Taxon	Site	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Riffle A	Riffle B
<i>Somatochlora sp.</i>		+	3	12	+	4 +	3 +
Gomphidae							
Lestidae							
<i>Lestes sp.</i>							
Libellulidae							
<i>Plathemis sp.</i>					+		
Lepidoptera							
Pyralidae							
<i>Acentria sp.</i>							
Hemiptera (true bug)							
Belostomatidae							
<i>Belostoma sp.</i>							+
Corixidae (water boatman)							
Corixini							
<i>Palmacorixa sp.</i>							
<i>Sigara sp.</i>		8 +	29 +	3 +	10 +		
<i>Trichocorixa sp.</i>						401 +	859 +
Gerridae							
<i>Trepobates sp.</i>							
Notonectidae (backswimmer)							
<i>Notonecta sp.</i>				+			+
Megaloptera							
Corydalidae (helgrammite)							
<i>Chauliodes sp.</i>							
Sialidae							
<i>Sialis sp.</i>				3 +	6 +		
Trichoptera (caddisfly)							
Hydropsychidae							
<i>Cheumatopsyche sp.</i>		22 +	8 +	3 +			
<i>Hydropsyche sp.</i>							
Hydroptilidae		2	2				
Leptoceridae							
<i>Oecetis sp.</i>		3		9	23 +		2
Coleoptera (beetle)							
Dytiscidae							
<i>Hydroporus sp.</i>							
<i>Laccophilus sp.</i>						+	
<i>Liodessus sp.</i>							
<i>Ilybius sp.</i>				1			
<i>Oreodytes sp.</i>							
<i>Thermonectus sp.?</i>					+		
Elmidae (riffle beetle)							
<i>Dubiraphia sp.</i>		307 +	343 +	383 +	324 +	17	18
<i>Stenelmis sp.</i>		28 +	17 +	4 +	14		
Gyrinidae							
<i>Gyrinus sp.</i>				+	+		
Haliplidae							
<i>Peltodytes sp.</i>		3 +	66 +	7 +	1 +	11	5 +
Hydrophilidae							
<i>Berosus sp.</i>			1	+	+	16 +	5 +
<i>Enochrus sp.</i>		+		+			
<i>Helophorus sp.</i>				+			
<i>Hydrochara sp.</i>							1
<i>Hydrophilus sp.</i>							
<i>Tropisternus sp.</i>						+	
Lampyridae							

		2007					
Taxon	Site	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Riffle A	Riffle B
Scirtidae							
<i>Prionocyphon sp.</i>		+					
Diptera (true fly)							
Ceratopogonidae (no-see-um)							
<i>Atrichopogon sp.</i>							
<i>Bezzia or Palpomyia sp.</i>		4	64	4			
Chironomidae (midge)							
Tribe Chironomini							
<i>Apedilum sp.</i>		+	4				
<i>Chironomus sp.</i>		30	4	140	910 +	1 +	+
<i>Cryptochironomus sp.</i>		12	45		48	533 +	785
<i>Cryptotendipes sp.</i>		32		8	17		262
<i>Dicrotendipes sp.</i>		8	16	8 +	32	1 +	131 +
<i>Endochironomus sp.</i>							
<i>Goeldichironomus sp.</i>							
<i>Microtendipes sp.</i>							
<i>Parachironomus sp.</i>							
<i>Paralauterborniella sp.</i>							
<i>Paratendipes sp.</i>				4			
<i>Phaenopsectra sp.</i>					16		
<i>Polypedilum sp.</i>		29	4	+		797	
<i>Pseudochironomus sp.</i>				4		1	
<i>Stichtochironomus sp.</i>		8		32	20		1
Tribe Tanytarsini							
<i>Cladotanytarsus sp.</i>				+			
<i>Paratanytarsus sp.</i>		51	33	+	48 +		
<i>Rheotanytarsus sp.</i>		+	1 +				
<i>Tanytarsus sp.</i>		13	43	56 +	111 +	1461 +	1575 +
<i>Zavrelia sp.</i>							
Subfamily Orthocladiinae							
<i>Corynoneura sp.</i>							
<i>Cricotopus sp.</i>							
<i>Euryhopsis sp.</i>							
<i>Nanocladius sp.</i>					+		
<i>Orthocladius sp.</i>			8		16 +		
<i>Parakiefferiella sp.</i>							
<i>Smittia sp.</i>							
Subfamily Tanypodinae							
<i>Clinotanypus sp.</i>				4	28 +	3	3
<i>Krenopelopia sp.</i>				+			
<i>Labrundinia sp.</i>							
<i>Natarsia sp.</i>			5		19		
<i>Pentaneura sp.</i>							
<i>Psectrotanypus sp.</i>				4	+		135
<i>Procladius sp.</i>		12		48	61 +	129 +	1 +
<i>Reomyia sp.</i>							
<i>Tanypus sp.</i>					1	4261 +	3114 +
<i>Thienemamimyia grp.</i>		14 +	102 +		56 +		1080
<i>Zavrelimyia sp.</i>							
Culicidae (mosquito)							
<i>Aedes sp.</i>			+				
<i>Anopheles sp.</i>							
<i>Culex sp.</i>							
Dixidae							
<i>Dixella sp.</i>							
Empididae							

		2007					
Taxon	Site	OW Down A	OW Down B	Down A	Down B	Riffle A	Riffle B
<i>Hemerodromia sp.</i>			9				
<i>Ramphomyia sp.</i>							
Ephydriidae (not keyed)			8		12		
Sciomyzidae							
Simuliidae (black fly)							
<i>Ectemnia sp. ?</i>							
<i>Simulium sp.</i>							
Stratiomyidae							
<i>Nemotelus sp. ?</i>		1					
<i>Ondontomyia sp.</i>		1 +	2				
<i>Stratiomys sp.</i>		1					
Tipulidae (crane fly)							
<i>Tipula sp.</i>		2	1 +				
Gastropoda (snail)							
Ancylidae (limpet)							
<i>Ferrissia sp.</i>		1	4	4	2		
Lymnaeidae (pond snail)							
<i>Fossaria sp.</i>		1	3	8 +	1 +		
<i>Stagnicola sp.</i>							
Physidae (pouch snail)							
<i>Physella sp.</i>		3 +	2	10 +	+	28 +	31 +
Planorbidae (ram's-horn snail)							
<i>Helisoma sp.</i>							
Pleuroceridae (riffle snail)							
<i>Elimia sp.</i>		236 +	163 +	489 +	230 +		
Bivalvia (clam, mussel)							
Sphaeriidae (fingernail clam)							
<i>Musculium sp.</i>						1	
<i>Pisidium sp.</i>		24	20	852 +	524 +	10	9
<i>Sphaerium sp.</i>		147 +	198 +	1401,9 +	734 +	10	9
Total Taxa either quant or qual		36 18	39 14	35 29	35 33	25 18	27 16
Total individuals		1039	1276	3595,9	3388	7973	8468
Total All Taxa		41	40	47	48	30	31

2007 total
25740